

**A STUDY ON CONSUMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS
SELF HELP GROUP PRODUCTS WITH SPECIAL
REFERENCE TO POLLACHI TALUK**

Dr. S. Premalatha* & A. Malarvizhi**

* Dean, Department of Commerce, Sree Ramu College of Arts and Science,
Pollachi, Tamilnadu

** Research Scholar, Department of Commerce, Sree Ramu College of Arts and Science, Pollachi, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Dr. S. Premalatha & A. Malarvizhi, "A Study on Consumer Satisfaction towards Self Help Group Products with Special Reference to Pollachi Taluk", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 103-108, 2018.

Abstract:

Today self help groups plays a crucial role in rural and urban areas by manufacturing and selling the products. It is considered as one of the most significant tools to adopt participatory approach for the economic empowerment of women. In present days many women entrepreneurs are came forward and follow some innovative strategies for selling their products and face a stiff competition between groups. In this way they have attaining the target it is very difficult task for every self help group women's. So, they are mainly focused on customers and their satisfaction then only survey the target market. Self help group provides better services and follow some innovative tactics are used to producing products, affordable price, proper place new ideas for promotion. In this study mainly focused on customer satisfaction towards self help group products in pollachi, factors that influence the consumers to purchase SHGs products, the level satisfaction of customers towards self help group products.

Key Words: Customer Satisfaction, Innovative Strategies & Affordable Price

In today's highly competitive market place, the survival of a firm depends upon how well they satisfy their customers. Customer satisfaction is a key to a business concern which helps them in development of their business concern. SHGs are considered as one of the most significant tools to adopt participatory approach for the economic empowerment of women, SHG is a group of people that meets regularly to discuss issues of interest to them and to look at solutions of commonly experienced problems. The group may or may not be promoted by Government or non-Government institutions. The role of self help groups is the upliftment of families in suffering is much appreciable. Each group selects one animator and two representatives from among themselves. The animator is responsible for providing leadership to the group and to maintain the various registers. The representatives assist the animator and maintain the bank accounts of the group. Self Help Groups are producing different types of products like masala items, food products, metal jewellerys, blankleds / bedspreads, soft toys and handloom sarees etc.

Literature Review:

Prakash R and Motilal Nehru S (1998) "Marketing of self help group products" stated in their article that, Kerala, the southernmost state of India has a wide variety of plantation and food crops. In order to develop the horticulture sector, the Kerala Horticulture Development Programme was set up in 1993. This programme aims at enhancing and sustaining the income of participating farmers through organic farming practices and appropriate marketing. The organization of self help groups was successful, as these proved to be effective and boosted the confidence of the farmers who were able to fetch a fair price for their produce.

The Hindu National News Paper (2009)¹⁰ wrote that Kodachadri Vaibhav, was a week-long exhibition-cum-sale of products prepared by self-help groups, expressing satisfaction over the improvement in the quality of products manufactured by self-help groups resulting in demand for them, a major problem confronting them was the lack of proper marketing arrangement to encourage the sale of their products. Self-help groups from other districts, too had displayed and exhibited their products at the exhibition, and received encouraging response.

Pawan Kumar Dhiman and Amita Rani (2010)¹¹ "Rural Marketing through Self-Help Groups (SHGs): A Case Study of Fatehabad District of Haryana (INDIA)". The main objective of their study is to assess the marketing practices of the SHGs to promote sale of their products/services in selected district of Haryana. In order to achieve high economic growth it has to mobilize and utilize all resources available in its environment including human resources. Women represents significant portion of the world's population, however they were not been utilized to the fuller in any developing economies. This women folk can act as an engine of economic development and industrialization. So, her participation is most important in all fields to faster the economic growth, including entrepreneurship. Women entrepreneurship in a formalized sense is a relatively new phenomenon in India. The present paper tries to through light on economic development through women entrepreneurship, their marketing strategies, profitability portion and problems faced by them in order to run their micro, tiny and small enterprises successfully. This empirical study was conducted in district Fatehabad of state Haryana. The researcher had collected the data from two blocks comprising data of 74 sampled SHG's leaders of district Fatehabad (Haryana) through designed schedule by conducting interview and observation

method and it had been found that these groups were not earning good profits due to lack of marketing knowledge, awareness and lack of appropriate marketing strategies.

Umamaheswari, R.Bhuvaneshwari and V. Bhuvaneshwari (2014)²¹ made a study on consumer preference towards self help group products outlet with special reference to selected groups in Coimbatore city. From this study, they attempt to identify that the consumers' major mean of awareness is through melas and they can make an extra effort to create more awareness of their products to the general public and they can do it by making innovative and attractive products that may influence more customers to purchase self help group products. The members have to get more trained staff that may help the customers and may influence them to purchase and they must also be well trained, and have to introduce more collections and variety of products in their outlets for increasing the sales.

Haripada data (2016)²⁵ "Self Help Groups in Tripura and Marketing of the Product: an Overview". The principle objectives of the study are to Analyses the necessary step be taken to improve the marketing linkages for the products. The primary data have been collected from 150 respondents through convenience sampling technique. This study is an attempt to review and analyze the causes, problems and future perspective of SHG movement in Tripura and also to search some suggestive solutions.

Statement of the Problem:

Self help group provide mutual support to the family earnings. SGHs are considered as one of the most significant tools to adopt participatory approach for the economic empowerment of women. Customer's satisfaction has become an important point of differentiate in SHGs products with other products consumers will spend more amount of money an being satisfied by the purchase of SHGs products as an initiators, users, influencers deciders, approvers and buyers.

Customer satisfaction is a function of products perceived between performance and customer expectations recognizing the high level of satisfaction leads to higher consumer loyalty, SHG products shout aim for total consumer satisfaction. There is a need for popularizing the new technique, development and business opportunities offered by SGG products. If the consumers are satisfied automatically the SHG products will become a superfluous industry. Hence it becomes necessary to assess the satisfaction level of consumers through a market survey.

Thus, a research has undertaken to find out solution to questions such as,

- ✓ How the customers know about SHG products?
- ✓ How long they have been using SHG products?
- ✓ Which factor influenced customers to purchase SHG products?
- ✓ Are the consumers satisfied with SHG products
- ✓ What is the level of satisfaction of customers with regarding to various factors like price, quality, packaging, reliability, discount, taste etc.?

Hence, an attempt has been made to study the consumer satisfaction towards Self Help Group Products with special reference to Pollachi Taluk.

Objectives of the Study :

The study has been carried on with the following objectives.

- ✓ To study the consumer satisfaction towards Self Help Group Products with special reference to Pollachi Taluk.
- ✓ To understand the origin and development SHG and SHG's Products
- ✓ To find out the factors that influences the consumers to purchase SHGs products.
- ✓ To examine the level of satisfaction of consumers towards SHGs products.
- ✓ To suggest suitable measures for the improvement of SHGs products.

Methodology:

Methodology is the way to solve the research problems systematically. It may be understood as a science of studying how researcher is done scientifically. The researcher has selected a particular place randomly for this survey. Data has been collected through questionnaire.

Sources of Data: Data collection is one of the most important aspects of research. The data was collected from both primary and secondary data for this study.

Primary Data: The primary data is the first hand source of information. The primary data was collected by distribution of questionnaires to the respondents. The questionnaires was prepared in such a way that they are simple and easy understandable. So the respondents were enabled to express their opinion and frankly.

Secondary Data: The secondary data have been collected from the periodicals, magazines, journals and websites.

Sampling Area: The study has been carried out in and around Pollachi Taluk. It is an agricultural oriented Taluk surrounded by villages. Pollachi is 40 kilometers from Coimbatore on the way to Parambikulam-Aliyar project. It is a leading town of the district and an important commercial centre.

Sample Size: The size of sample chosen for the study is 200.

Sampling Method: Convenience sampling method is used for the study. This type of sampling is very convenient and is relatively inexpensive.

Study Period: The field work for the study was carried on by the researcher during January 2016 to June 2016.

Framework of Analysis: The study has been analyzed using the following statistical tools.

- ✓ Simple percentage analysis
- ✓ Chi-square test
- ✓ Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Hypothesis of the Study: The following are the hypothesis under the study

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant association between area of residence of the respondents and their level of satisfaction on Self Help Group products.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant association between age of the respondents and their level of satisfaction on Self Help Group products.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant association between gender of the respondents and their level of satisfaction on Self Help Group products.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant association between occupation of the respondents and their level of satisfaction on Self Help Group products.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ Only 200 respondents are selected for the study.
- ✓ The survey is limited to in and around of Pollachi Taluk and the study cannot be generalized to other geographical locations.
- ✓ The size of sampling comparing to the population in the Pollachi Taluk chosen is very less and hence it may not be a whole representation of population in total Taluk.
- ✓ Consumer behavior is dynamic; there is every possibility that the findings of today may become invalid tomorrow.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

Area of Residence of the Respondents		
Area of Residence	No of Respondents	Percentage
Rural	144	72
Urban	56	28
Total	200	100
Age of the Respondents		
Age	No of Respondents	Percentage
Below 25 Years	44	22
26 - 30 Years	54	27
31 - 35 Years	36	18
Above 35 Years	66	33
Total	200	100
Gender of the Respondents		
Gender	No of Respondents	Percentage
Male	68	34
Female	132	66
Total	200	100
Marital Status of the Respondents		
Marital Status	No of Respondents	Percentage
Married	120	60
Unmarried	80	40
Total	200	100
Educational Qualification of the Respondents		
Educational Qualification	No of Respondents	Percentage
Post Graduate	62	31
Under Graduate	70	35
Up to Higher Secondary Level	38	19
Illiterate	30	15
Total	200	100
Occupation of the Respondents		
Occupation	No of Respondents	Percentage
Business	48	24
Employed	60	30
Housewife	46	23

Student	22	11
Agriculturist	24	12
Total	200	100
Type of Family of the Respondents		
Types Of Family	No of Respondents	Percentage
Nuclear Family	130	65
Joint Family	70	35
Total	200	100
Monthly Income of the Respondents		
Family Monthly Income	No of Respondents	Percentage
Below Rs.10,000/-	38	19
Rs.10,001/- To Rs.20,000/-	52	27
Rs.20,001/- To Rs.30,000/-	48	23
Rs.30,001/- To Rs.40,000/-	26	13
Above Rs.40,000/-	36	18
Total	200	100

Chi-Square Analysis:

Area of Residence and Level of Satisfaction				
Area	High	Moderate	Low	Total
Rural	74 (51.38%)	50 (34.72%)	20 (13.88%)	144
Urban	20 (35.71%)	24 (42.85%)	12 (21.42%)	56
Total	94	74	32	200
Age and Level of Satisfaction				
Age	High	Moderate	Low	Total
Below 25 years	36 (54.54%)	20 (30.30%)	10 (15.15%)	66
26 - 30 years	20 (37.03%)	24 (44.44%)	10 (18.51%)	54
31 - 35 years	20 (55.55%)	8 (22.22%)	8 (22.22%)	36
Above 35 years	18 (40.90%)	22 (50.0%)	4 (9.09%)	44
Total	94	74	32	200
Gender and Level of Satisfaction				
Gender	High	Moderate	Low	Total
Male	40 (58.82%)	22 (32.35%)	6 (8.82%)	68
Female	54 (40.90%)	52 (39.39%)	26 (19.69%)	132
Total	94	74	32	200
Occupation and Level of Satisfaction				
Occupation	High	Moderate	Low	Total
Business	28 (58.33%)	12 (25.00%)	8 (16.66%)	48
Employed	28 (46.66%)	24 (40.0%)	8 (13.33%)	60
Housewife	22 (47.82%)	18 (39.13%)	6 (13.04%)	46
Student	8 (36.36%)	8 (36.36%)	6 (27.27%)	22
Agriculturist	8 (33.33%)	12 (50.0%)	4 (16.6%)	24
Total	94	74	32	200

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA):

Area of Residence and Level of Satisfaction					
Sources of variation	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.859	2	0.430	2.144	0.120
Within Groups	39.461	197	0.200		
Total	40.320	199			
Age and Level of Satisfaction					
Sources of variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.398	2	1.199	.913	.403
Within Groups	258.782	197	1.314		
Total	261.180	199			
Gender and Level of Satisfaction					
Sources of variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.567	2	.783	3.563	0.030
Within Groups	43.313	197	.220		
Total	44.880	199			

Occupation and Level of Satisfaction					
Sources of variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	7.902	2	3.951	2.394	0.094
Within Groups	325.118	197	1.650		
Total	333.020	199			

Summary of Findings:

When the area of the residence, age, marital status, educational qualification and occupation is compared with level of satisfaction in the self help group products, there is no significant relationship between area of residence, age, marital status, educational qualification and occupation and level of satisfaction on self help group products. On the basis of testing gender, type of family and family monthly income with level of satisfaction in the self help group products, there is significant relationship between gender, type of family, family monthly income and level of satisfaction on self help group products. On the basis of testing gender, type of family and level of satisfaction, there is no significant relationship between gender, type of family and the level of satisfaction of self help group products. On the basis of testing area of residence, age, marital status, educational qualification, occupation, family monthly income and level of satisfaction, there is a significant relationship between area of residence, age, marital status, educational qualification, occupation, family monthly income and the level of satisfaction of self help group products.

Suggestions:

On the basis of above findings, the researcher suggests measures that may help to increase the customer satisfaction of Self Help Group Products. The customer suggested creating awareness of the Self Help Group Products through advertisements. Pricing of Self Help Group Products may be made with discounts and gifts. Updated technology may be used to produce more products with reasonable price. Self Help Group Products helps to develop the economy of a Nation. So, Government should take necessary steps to promote Self Help Groups.

Conclusion:

The present study reveals that the self help groups are working hard' to satisfy their customers. Self help group products are more but the customers prefer to purchase only some products. The majority of the respondents feel that self help group products are home-made and eco-friendly. So, they recommend it to their friends and relatives. The products are to be processed well as it likely to be influenced by the changing global scenario. New methods, technologies, innovative products etc will be helps to characterize the future development. Further, new development is the only factor which helps to satisfy the customers of Self Help Group Products and to utilize it potential in the growing industry.

References:

1. Prakash R. and Motilal Nehru S., "Marketing produce through self help groups", LEISA Magazine, 14 December 1998 p.16.
2. Steven P. Segal Dina Redman and Carol Siverman "Measuring Clients' Satisfaction with Self-Help Agencies, 2000, p.208.
3. National Resources Institute "The Role of SHGs in Rural Non-Farm Employment", Discussion paper produced by Barbara Adolph for the project. 63, 2003.
4. K.G andhi and N. Udayakumari "Marketing strategies for self help group products" Indian Journal of Current Research and Academic Review, 2006 p.21.
5. Ciavolino. E & Dahlgaard. J. J. "Customer satisfaction modeling and analysis: A case study", Journal of Total Quality Management, 2007 18(5), 545-554.
6. Kumaran, M., Rengarajan, S "Self-Help Groups - Prospective Channel Partners for the Promotion of Consumer Products in Tamil Nadu's Rural Markets", Marketing Mastermind, April 2008.
7. K. Raghupati Bhat "Market products made by women SHGs, Udupi, September 9, 2009.
8. K.V eerakumar (2016) article titled "A Study on Impact of Customer Satisfaction on Brand Loyalty" International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education, Vol-I, Issue-I, June – 2016. P.No.661-663.
9. Yuvarani R., "Rural products: Industry's role, scope, opportunities and challenges", Article Base, 6 May 2009.
10. Vaddi. S and Bhalakrishnaiah. B "consumer awareness and consumer behavior towards self help group products" 2009 p.124-128
11. The Hindu National News Paper, "Lack of marketing hinders growth of self-help groups" Jan 17, 2009.
12. Pawan Kumar Dhiman and Amita Rani "Rural Marketing through Self-Help Groups (SHGs): A Case Study of Fatehabad District of Haryana (INDIA)" ISBN: 978-1-63415-833-6 July 2010 Paper ID: V5721
13. Ravindra Bhavan, "Rural Marketing to the Self Help Group" International Journal of Business and Management Tomorrow, 2011 Vol. 1 No. 1.

14. Meena K. R., Muthumani S., Shanthi B, "Women Self Help Groups: An initiative for Marketing Aquaculture Product for Sustainable Livelihood" 2011 p.124-128
15. Vimala. D, Ravisankar, "Growth of Self Help Group products:" International Journal in Management and social Science 2011 Vol.03 Issue-07, page258.
16. S. Anbu Malar, "Consumers attitude and preferences towards self help group products" Asia-Pacific Business Review Publisher 2012 Volume: 4 Source Issue: 2
17. Dr. K. Rajendran, "Customer satisfaction of SHGs with the Primary Agricultural Cooperative Societies (PACS): Evidences from the field" International Journal of Research in Social Sciences 2012 Volume 2, Issue 3 294.
18. N. Udayakumari (2012) Growth strategies. Marketing Strategies of Women Self Help Groups international journal of current research and academic review ISSN: 2347-3215 Volume 1 Number 2 (2013) pp. 117-122.
19. V. Krishnaveni & Dr. R. Haridas, "SHGS Product and its Marketing Problems" Livestock Research for Rural Development, Volume 2, Number 2, February 2013.
20. A. Vennila and Dr. K. Shanmugasundaram "level of satisfaction by the women members of self help groups" – namakkal dist International Journal of Marketing, financial services & management research issno 2277- 3622 vol.2, no. 6, June (2013) pp 157-168.
21. S. Alexander and Dr. R. Selvaraj "Marketing of Self Help Groups Products" Marketing of Self Help Groups Products 2014 Vol. 5 Issue – 2.
22. Umamaheswari, R. Bhuvaneshwari and V. Bhuvaneshwari, BEST: International Journal of Management, Information Technology and Engineering (BEST: IJMITE) Vol. 2, Issue 1, Jan 2014, 33-42.
23. T. Thileepan (2014) "E-Marketing For Self Help Group's Agricultural Products in India", ISSN 0976-6510 (Online) Volume 5, Issue 1, January (2014), pp. 46-52.
24. M. Gurupandi (2015), "Marketing strategies of Self Help Group Products in Krishnagiri District". ISSN: Impact Factor: Volume Issue - 5 | - 6 | - 2015.
25. M. D. Palanivel, "Marketing Problems Encountered by the Self-Help Groups Members - An Analysis", Indian Journal of Marketing Vol.XLI, No.10, pp.4-8.
26. Haripada Data, "Self Help Groups in Tripura and Marketing of the Product: an Overview" Research Paper Volume: 6 | Issue: 1, pp.71-82.
27. Rekha Yadav and M. P. Sagar" Perceived constraints and associated factors of dairy based women selfhelp groups (SHGs) in Rewari district of Haryan" International Journal of Sociology and Anthropology Vol.8 (3), pp. 23-26.
28. Journal of Marketing research
29. Journal of Marketing studies
30. Journal of Marketing Education
31. Journal of Total Quality Management
32. Journal of Management Research
33. Indian Journal of Current Research and Academic Review
34. International Journal of Business and Management Tomorrow
35. International Journal of Research in Social Sciences
36. International Journal of Consumer studies
37. International Journal of Marketing Studies
38. International Journal of Research in Finance and marketing
39. International Journal of Marketing, Financial Services & Management Research
40. International Journal of Sociology and Anthropology
41. LEISA Magazine
42. www.megselfhelp.gov.in
43. www.icmrr.org
44. www.indianresearchjournals.com
45. www.ijmrr.com
46. jmr.indianjournals.com
47. www.indianjournalofmanagement.com